

AM3—an induced rice mutant with improved grain size and yield

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Abhilash (IET5882), a variety derived from CR63-6218/Pankaj, was released for cultivation in zones 8 (upland) and 9 (rainfed lowland) of Karnataka, India, in 1985. This improved variety has several acceptable agronomic traits: long duration (150 d), medium height (110 cm), high yield (5 t ha⁻¹), and tolerance for blast and major insect pests such as stem borers and leafhoppers. Its only unacceptable feature is its long and medium bold grains. Therefore, through induced mutagenesis, an attempt was made to recover mutants with slender grains while retaining all other traits of Abhilash intact.

One thousand mature seeds (M₀) of Abhilash were exposed to γ (gamma) irradiation (25 kr) at Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Mumbai, India. The M₁ seeds were grown in the field at the Agricultural Research Station (zone 9 of Karnataka) during the 2000 wet season (WS) (Jun-Dec). During harvest, care was taken to collect panicles only from the main tiller. The seeds were bulked (Joshua 2000) to grow the M₂ (10,000 plants) during the 2001 WS. Seeds from 74 selected individual plants were advanced to the M₄ generation. Eight mutants were finally selected and grown in 2 × 3-m plots with three replications to evaluate the stability of the mutant phenotype and other agronomic traits in the M₅ generation during the 2005 WS. The parent variety (Abhilash) and

Table 1. Performance of Abhilash and its mutants at the Agricultural Research Station, Sirsi, Karnataka, India, 2005 wet season.

Parent/mutant/ check	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Kernel size (mm)			Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
			Length (L)	Breadth (B)	L/B	
AM3	124.00	97.80	7.37	2.33	3.16	4.7
Abhilash	124.00	96.07	6.90	2.80	2.47	4.5
AM68	131.33	77.13	5.33	2.67	2.00	4.5
Intan	124.00	109.60	6.97	2.23	3.12	4.3
AM46	135.33	79.80	5.80	2.97	1.96	4.1
AM36	140.00	91.67	5.67	2.70	2.10	4.0
AM23	125.00	93.27	6.97	2.57	2.72	3.9
AM31	121.33	114.00	7.57	2.50	3.03	3.5
AM49	124.33	95.40	7.50	2.43	3.09	3.2
AM4	115.33	97.87	8.13	2.10	3.88	3.1
CV	0.24	3.04	4.94	4.49	7.67	9.87

a variety released for zones 8 and 9 in 1974 with superior grain size (Intan) were used as checks.

Preference for grain size and shape varied from one group of consumers to another. (For general consumption, kernel length-breadth ratio (L/B) between 2.5 and 3.0 is acceptable as long as kernel length is more than 6 mm [Kaul 1970].) In general, long grains are preferred in the Indian subcontinent. Four mutants (AM31, AM49, AM3, and AM4) with an L/B value significantly more than that of Abhilash were recovered (Table 1). These mutants had kernel length more than 7 mm. Compared with Abhilash, AM3 and AM49 did not show any significant difference in terms of days to 50% flowering and plant height. Interestingly, AM3 had a marginally higher yield than the parent and Intan. Therefore,

Table 2. Performance of AM3 in five locations, Karnataka, India, 2006 wet season.

Parent/mutant/ check	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			
	Sirsi (2) ^a	Mundgod (2)	Mugad (1)	% increase
AM3	6.3	6.5	5.0	
Abhilash	5.5	6.1	4.9	7.9
Intan	5.1	4.8	3.6	31.9

^aNumber of test locations.

it looks most promising with its improved kernel shape and size, and marginal yield advantage over the parent. Because AM3 has all the other desirable agronomic characters, it could be highly acceptable to consumers. AM4, with exceptionally slender (L/B of 3.95) and long kernels (8.13 mm), might be prone to breakage during milling. AM3 was tested in five different locations for agronomic and yield traits

during the 2006 Wet season. It recorded 7.9% and 31.9% higher yield than checks Abhilash and Intan, respectively (Table 2).

References

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